

Conceptual Analysis of Recreational Activities in Rural Tourism: A Study in Sinop Province

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ABSTRACT

Sinop Province has a very convenient structure in terms of the use and development of rural tourism activities. The city, which home to different bird species, lakes, waterfalls, nature park, plateaus and many other natural beauties in the region, is also rich in cultural and historical terms. The aim of the study is to examine and develop rural tourism recreational activities in the province of Sinop. The study aims to increase the demand for rural tourism, to ensure the development of rural facilities, and to evaluate the infrastructure and superstructure by examining the recreational activities carried out within the scope of rural tourism in the province of Sinop from a conceptual perspective. The research is important in terms of supporting the socio-cultural and economic development of the people of the region, strengthening the relationship with the tourist, contributing to the development of the region. It is important in terms of contributing to the development of the region, its sustainability and the correct use of productive natural areas that can be brought into tourism.

1. Introduction

Tourists looking for diversity have turned to alternative types of tourism within the scope of special interest tourism in response to mass tourism. Alternative types of tourism can be considered as restorative in order to prevent the destruction of social, cultural and psychological areas. The importance of rural tourism can be emphasized by the protection, sustainability of natural areas and thus positively affecting values. Tourists who want to get away from urban life have turned to rural areas to be intertwined with nature. Alternative recreational activities have occurred under the heading of rural tourism for visitors who are sensitive to nature and the environment.

Recreational activities, importance of rural tourism in the tourism sector, characteristics, sustainability, effects on the local people, economic and at the same

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time This study, which is evaluated from a socio-cultural point of view, is evaluated within the scope of Sinop Province. Due to the location of Sinop Province and its natural beauties, its infrastructure and superstructure are evaluated within the scope of rural tourism and some recommendations are included.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Rural tourism

There have also been differences in the definition of tourism with globalization in the world. In general terms, those who are tired of urban life are looking for new searches and resting, traveling and having fun. it is considered as tourism that they carry out outside their place of residence. In order to make people happy psychologically, sociologically and culturally, the phenomenon they do temporarily is called tourism (Bahar & Kozak, 2008: 28). With the increase in mass tourism, the susceptible to nature, the environment, historical heritage and its sustainability, the destruction of the natural nature of the works has caused some social problems. As of 1970 and 1980, alternative types of tourism have been established to avoid this issue (Triarchi & Karamanis, 2017: 39). From this definition, the globalized world and people are carrying out the tourism movement for a variety of reasons. The idea of a holiday can vary from person to person. For this reason, alternative types of tourism have emerged in the tourism industry. One of them is rural tourism.

Rural tourism is considered to be activities in rural areas. It is for recreation and, in general, for leisure or business purposes. It is also a type of tourism that visitors from the same country or different countries can be defined as the use of rural areas of urban people, where tourists perform out of their permanent residency. This tourism activity takes place in areas that are several minutes or miles away. It is preferred by day or genre regardless of distance. Physical or emotional, sometimes physical satisfaction can also be referred to as emotional activity, called visits to family members, relatives. It has become difficult to make an identification in general due to differences in service of several purposes (Kurt, 2009: 15).

Environmentally friendly tourism types evaluated as part of alternative tourism have been highlighted and preferred in order to recognize the importance of environmental awareness, protection instinct and sustainability on earth from 1980 to present. The interaction between tourists and local people who are understanding and respectful of the socio-cultural values of the region to be visited is related (Sillignakis, 2014; İpar & Tırlı, 2014: 46). Interactions from different cultures without a corruption in rural cultures occur in this type of tourism. This allows local people to preserve and promote their culture in rural areas. Although it is perceived as different from each other, rural tourism, eco tourism, nature tourism, agritourism are evaluated in the same scope. The aim of all is to create an alternative type of tourism for sustainability and protection (Gokkur, 2017: 1).

2.1.2. Rural tourism characteristics

When the characteristics of rural tourism are evaluated, the relationship between tourists visiting the local people and the residents of the local community, which tourists experience and witness the lives of the local people. They try their products, they see the hand art of the local people closely, and they also experience different regional products in their kitchens. They are greeted as a friendly host, tasting specially grown agricultural products and continuing their travels with their hospitality tour (Gökkur, 2017: 1). Rural tourism, while most sources are also evaluated by the ability to experience farm life, is actually intertwined with nature and is considered as a part of the tourist tour of picnic areas in rural areas, camping activities in nature and resorts for environmentally friendly tourists (Koç & Şahin, 1999). Rural tourism is a key element in generation-to-generation transmission and keeping values alive, unlike the goal of causing the destruction of rural areas (Çetinkaya Karafaki & Yazgan, 2012). Based on these definitions, when assessing people's holiday insights, expectations, protection of areas and alternative tourism types for future generations, tourism mobility for rural areas can not only lead to tourism activity, but also the instinct for interacting with nature, tranquility, and peace difference can lead to this kind of tourism. Local people can be said to have a significant impact on prosperity and employment.

Rural tourism is a positive contribution to the region where the activity is being done economically, when considered as rural development, but also an important kind of tourism for the sustainability and protection of the area. It is considered a phenomenon that embraces the concept of economicism. Rural tourism, which plays a key role in the economic development of the local people, also has an important place in the tourism sector (Baykal & Toprak, 2010).

2.1.3. Economic and socio-cultural evaluation

The effects of rural tourism are mentioned and the socio-cultural and economic effects are addressed. In terms of economically, rural areas contribute to rural tourism and income sources in addition to agriculture. Employment is one of the problems in rural tourism. Tourism mobility in rural areas also brings employment. With the outbreak of unemployment in rural tourism, the migration movement from these areas to the cities is being prevented, and in this case, regional development is also said to be an issue. It is mentioned that the need to improve infrastructure is the result of tourism activity in rural areas and that there are improvements. It is also observed that women's employment contributes to the family economy. It is mentioned that the country has taken a share in its sectors, which are indirectly coalitions with increased income (Çeken & Ekici, 2018: 47-48). Based on definitions, it can be said that as the demand for rural tourism increases, it will have a positive impact on the region and the regional economy, as well as being more conscious about the protection of natural and cultural areas, both jobs and areas have an important role in improving and transferring to future generations.

2.2. Recreational activities in rural tourism

Recreation is for the purpose of satisfaction in line with their own free will and desires, except for the work that individuals have to do voluntary leisure activities (Kesim, 2016: 132). According to Butler (1959: 3), recreation is a free-time event to gain different experiences other than compulsory work. According to Bayer (1992: 205), recreation is a variety of activities that people do in free time zones. Based on all of these free time definitions, recreation can be defined as the activities that individuals do in order to get away from everyday stress elements and to get spiritual pleasure, except for the work that they do necessarily.

The demand for a recreational that has become an important concept in people's lives has also increased day by day (Yayla & Karaçar, 2019: 35). In addition to the increase in motivation in individuals following the recreational activities, there is a significant reduction in negative influences due to environmental factors (Özer & Çavuşoğlu, 2014). People prefer natural and open spaces in the long distance of busy and stressful city life to carry out recreational activities (Yayla & Karaçar, 2019: 35). People may say they prefer open spaces more than urban areas to do recreational activities. The recreational activities that people usually prefer more to avoid feeling psychologically well and stress than urban recreational events are activities that people can access both their short and long leisure time and do by going out of the city they are in (Karaküçük, 2008: 80). Rural recreational activities are leisure, sports, and recreational activities that take place in a day or longer period, depending on the duration of their stay, by going to a natural area outside the city (Özgüç, 1984: 7). With these definitions of Karaküçük (2008) and Özgüç (1984), it can be said that by diversifying the open space as a urban and rural place, recreational activities can vary by location and that the existing relationship with each other can be observed in all open spaces.

2.2.1. Source-based recreation events in rural areas

The resource-based recreational event in rural areas covers recreational activities that are used for recreational activities, where people are intertwined with nature and nature offers opportunities for recreational events. For example, fishing, hiking, camping, mountain biking, activities such as rock climbing, boating and hunting are included in this category. Examples of forests, national parks, rivers and seaside are the areas where resource-based recreational activities are to be carried out. In resource-centered environments, nature itself is the foundation of fun and enjoyment (Jensen & Guthrie, 2006).

2.2.2. Intermediary central recreation events in rural areas

Intermediary recreational activities in rural areas include activities that individuals perform in natural environments outside the city to reduce the physical and mental fatigue that they experience in urban life. For this type of activity, a combination of both source and user-focused outdoor recreation can be used. Water

skiing, sailing, canoe, cycling, swimming, safari, horseback riding, picnic, animal watching, archery, activities such as boating trips are examples.

2.2.3. User-centered recreation events in rural areas

Intermediary recreation activities in rural areas are usually based on the site. Recreative activities normally performed in unnatural and later modified artificial recreative areas. These activities include outdoor theaters, concerts, fairs and fireworks. Such open spaces are usually close to the city center and are easily accessible to people. Zoos, playgrounds, track and field areas, municipal facilities are used for user-focused activities (Jensen & Guthrie, 2006).

3. Methodology

The aim of the research is to determine the rural recreation routes and the areas that can be visited in the province of Sinop. In this study, literature review and document analysis, which is one of the qualitative research methods, was carried out. In the study, an index study was prepared about the researches on the concept of recreation and the content of these studies. It was carried out by reviewing the national and international theses and articles that could be accessed within the scope of the research, and some routes belonging to the province of Sinop were determined. According to datas, recreation routes for rural tourism has been carried out.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Sinop rural tourism recreation potential

Sinop Province has a very convenient structure in terms of the use and development of rural tourism activities. The city, which home to different bird species, lakes, waterfalls, nature parks, plateaus, the “ria” type coast which is located only Norway and Hamsilos Bay in the World, caves, castles, historical sides and architectural structures, local handicrafts and culinary culture, echological farms, and home to many more beauties. Sinop Province is a peninsula consisting of Ince Burun and Boztepe (Ada) parts in the part far north of Turkey. The city where the population is low and the industrial area is not engaged in intensive activities, is one of the rare cities that has been awarded the title of “Happy City” (Sinop Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism, 2017). Below are the areas where rural tourism recreation activities are carried out in the province of Sinop and the routes created, and the potential areas that can be evaluated for this purpose are examined.

4.1.1. Tatlıca Waterfalls National Park

Tatlıca waterfalls, located in Tatlıca village in Erfelek district of Sinop Province, consists of 28 waterfalls shaped gradually by Gülleyük Stream. Its total length is 2 km. This area was declared as a “Natural Park” in 2011. Tatlıca Waterfalls Nature Park has the potential for many rural tourism recreation activities such as trekking, hiking, photography, botanical excursions, plant and animal watching, bird

watching, camping, picnic. Activities such as nature walks, waterfall climbing, picnic and camping can be done in all seasons of the year in the forest cover of the waterfalls and its surroundings. Potentially enhancing facilities such as the control unit, wc, country coffee, bakery, children play ground, wooden walking path and observation terrace installed in the area are also at the disposal of the visitors (Republic of Turkey 10th Region Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, 2022).

4.1.2. Hamsilos Nature Park – Hamsilos Bay – Akliman Bay

Hamsilos Natural Park is located in the Inceburun, which is called the northernmost part of Turkey. Hamsilos Bay, which is the 14 km away from the city center of Sinop, is in the form of ria type coast. Due to its ria type coast, the bay is also called fjord. Akliman Bay, located in the south of the area, has the feature of a natural harbor and has the potential to host many water sports. There are six endemic plant species such as wild clove, Kastamonu onion, thistle, goatee, spurge, and Sinop crocus in the area, which has a diverse biodiversity (Republic of Turkey 10th Region Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, 2022). Hamsilos Nature Park, which is a first-degree protected area, provides opportunities for activities such as botanical excursions, plant watching, trekking, photo safari, bird watching, camping, picnic with its ecological diversity and shelter potential of 150 different bird species. At the same time, Hamsilos Nature Park, which has an ideal environment for canoeing, hosts those who want to take canoe training, participants for competitions and followers of the annual canoe festival (General Directorate of Nature Conservation and National Parks, 2022).

4.1.3. Sarikum Nature Reserve

Sarikum nature protection area is a region that contains many touristic attractions such as sea, lake, desert and forest areas. It is 21 km from the center of Sinop. Of the 400 hectare area, 102 hectares are lakes, 82 hectares are swamps, and the rest is a 4 kilometer sandy beach and a forest area containing endemic plant species specific to the region. The lake is a lagoon lake formed by the coastal dunes covering the bay over the years (Republic of Turkey Sinop Governorate, 48-50).

In the surrounding woodland there is flora cover such as blackberries, rosehip, contracting, pine, oak, beech, ash ivy. It is home to different bird species and many wildlife environments in its ecological system. Species of animals such as roe deer, lynx, foxes, deer, wild yearling horses, ferrets etc. in the field and fish species such as kefal, dill and rockfish can be observed in the lake. This area, which has the characteristics of a bird paradise, is an ideal environment for bird watching as it has a suitable environment for bird species to spend the winter and is on the migration route of birds (Yılmaz, 2005: 6-7). Juniper, finch, woodpecker, crane, goldfinch, wren, robin, forest eagle, cormorant, etc. In addition to the species, six of the globally endangered bird species within the scope of ICUN criteria can be observed in this area (Özkoç et al., 2019). In the area where the bird watching tower is located, recreational activities such as camping, swimming, trekking, bicycle tours,

photography, botanical excursions and bird watching can be carried out (Aytuğ et al., 2020: 725-727).

4.1.4. Plateaus

The province of Sinop, located in the Black Sea Region, has vast and diverse plateau areas with its geographical location and climatic conditions. These plateaus are Gurfındık-Bozarmut plateau, Türkeli Kurugöl plateau, Ayancık Akgöl plateaus, Duragan Bozluk plateaus. In these areas, recreational activities such as nature walks, bicycle tours and picnics can be carried out (Aytuğ et al., 2020: 725-727).

4.1.5. Ecological farm and lands

World Wide Opportunities on Organic Farms Turkey (WWOOF Turkey, TATUTA) is a worldwide project that brings together volunteers and ecological producers to build a sustainable global society.⁵

Yüksel Baba Farm, which provides service within the scope of this project, is located in Kabalı village, 25 km from Sinop. In this facility, which has an accommodation area for 6 people, recreational activities such as agricultural production and participation in animal care, fruit picking, local food preparation are carried out. Guests can be choose to stay as volunteers or guests (İpar & Tırlı, 2014: 51).

Deydaa Ecological Camp is 5 km from Gerze district of Sinop Province. It is established in a land of 4 decares. With an accommodation capacity of 12 people and a tent area for 5 people, its distance to the sea is 100 meters. Permaculture agriculture is applied in the enterprise.⁶ Guests in the camping area can participate in activities such as agricultural production, fruit and vegetable harvesting, gardening, participation in local food production, cooking with products collected from the garden, trekking, hiking, campfire activities, barbecue (Sak & Erkol Bayram, 2020: 536).

4.1.6. Caves and basalt cliffs

İnaltı Cave is located in İnaltı village of Ayancık district of Sinop Province. The first 300 meters of the cave, which has a length of 658 meters, can be visited. Located at an altitude of 1070 m, stalactites, stalagmites, stalactites and limestones forming its foundation can be seen in the cave. There are excursion routes arranged in the cave and a forested area around it.⁷ In this area, which has a high rural tourism potential, recreational activities such as trekking, hiking, rock climbing, nature walks and bicycle tours can also be carried out.

Other potential caves in Sinop are Buzluk and Ağcaçal caves in Durağan district. Buzluk cave consists of sections in which there is intense air flow. In these

⁵ <https://wwoofturkey.org/>

⁶ <http://www.deydaa.com/>

⁷ <https://www.kulturportali.gov.tr/>

parts, natural ice formation takes place and glacier formation increases further due to the increased airflow in summer (İpar & Tırıl, 2014: 51).

Basalt Cliffs, located in Fındıklık region of Boyabat district, have a shape formed by the formation of rocks with 4-5-6 edges, 30-40 m high, located in three valleys close to each other (Republic of Turkey Sinop Governorate, 2022). The Cliffs have a strong recreation area potential for the province of Sinop (İpar & Tırıl, 2014: 51). Recreational activities such as nature walks, trekking, hiking, rock climbing, picnic and photo safari can be carried out in the Basalt Cliffs and the surrounding area.

4.1.7. Gastronomy

The contribution of local food and beverage culture to the formation of attractiveness and the image of the region in travels is quite large. Apart from the desire to eat in line with basic needs, people care about learning new cuisines and tasting new foods. One of the recreational activities carried out in rural tourism is learning to cook local dishes and tasting the dishes (Kesici & Mustafa, 2012). Sinop Province has its own local delicacies such as mantı, nokul, mamalika, folding-quince-chestnut dishes, starch halvah, tirit, gurnard soup, ıslama, atom, corn soup, chestnut-corn-Circassian cakes, içli tava, keskek, sırik kebab (Republic of Turkey Sinop Governorate, 42-46). The province, which has a strong potential with this feature, also offers the opportunity to perform these activities in the ecological camps and farms located in it.

Chestnut honey is produced in the districts of Boyabat, Duragan, Erfelek, Gerze, Sarayduzu and Turkeli in the province of Sinop, and it has become a nationwide brand. In the analysis of chestnut honey, pollen traces of 61 taxa were found (Özler, 2015). Chestnut honey production areas have high potential for rural tourism and api tourism recreation activities.

4.2. Sinop routes

4.2.1. Trekking routes

There are 37 trekking routes created in Sinop Province. These routes include different and interesting routes such as the routes where the participants can spend time alone with nature, see endemic plant species, villages, plateaus, waterfalls, historical ruins, and historical migration routes also called "Yörük Yolu". The top ten popular routes are listed below (Metin, 2018):

- Hamsilos – İnceburun (14 km), difficulty level 2;
- İnceburun – Sarıkum (13 km), difficulty level 2;
- Keçideresi – Kumludere (14 km), difficulty level 2;
- Saray Gölü – Akgöl (12 km), difficulty level 2;
- Salar Kaya Tomb – Basalt Cliffs (13 km), difficulty level 3;
- Çukurhan Castle – Kılıçlı Waterfalls (13 km), difficulty level 2;
- Çukurhan – Çeşnigir Plateau – Tırnalık (14 km), difficulty level 1;
- Tatlıca Waterfalls – Erfelek Dam Lake (10 km), difficulty level 2;

- Tatlıcak – Tırnalık – Yaylacık Plateau – Tatlıcak (12 km), difficulty level 2;
- Hacıağaç Plateau – Araplar (Handere) Plateau – Göldağı Plateau – Çatak Canyon (Kapaklıoluk) (13 km), difficulty level 3.

4.2.2. Jeep safari routes

Sinop Province has a rich potential for jeep safari tours, which is an important recreational activity for rural tourism. The jeep-safari tracks determined by the Ministry of Culture and Tourism for the province are given below (Sinop Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism, 2017).

- Sinop – İnceburun – Sarıkum – Sinop (42 km);
- Boyabat – İsaoglu pond – Kılıçlı Waterfalls – Çukurhan Plateau – Duvarçam Kirencükuru – Sazak – Acısu – Gerze (73 km);
- Durağan – Buzluk Plateau – Geyikardıcı – Uzunöz – Ahıska – Çağlayan (Tilkilik) – Sarımsak – Pirahmet – Gerze (88 km);
- Gerze – Bolalı – Suludüz – Çukurca Plateau – Kozfindık Yaylası – Bozarmut Plateau – Dikmen (94 km);
- Ayancık – Zaviye – Armutyazı – Kapıkaya – Hacıağaç Plateau – Handere – Araplar Plateau – Kuru Plateau – Gölet Plateau – Çatak Plateau – Çatak Canyon – Çatak – Gökçealan – Türkeli (135 km).

4.2.3. Cycling routes

In the province of Sinop, there are many bicycle path formations surrounded by forest areas, as well as bicycle paths including areas such as Hamsilos bay and Sarıkum nature park. There are also shops in the city center where they can rent bicycles for those who want to (İpar & Tırıl, 2014: 51). Apart from these, the Amasra-Sinop route offers an adventure opportunity of 331 km for those looking for a long-term route. In addition, there are tracks designated for bicycle tours by the Sinop Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism, and some of them are given below (Sinop Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism, 2017).

- Sinop – Akliman – Hamsilos – Akliman – Sinop (33 km);
- Ayancık – Yenikonak – Kepez Canyon – İnaltı Cave – Kızılcağaya Waterfalls – Duvarsökü – Yenikonak – Ayancık (62 km);
- Ayancık – Erfelek – Sinop (72 km);
- Sinop – Boyabat (92 km).

4.2.4. Paragliding routes

Yelken Tepe is located in Hacıselli village of Gerze district of Sinop Province. Paragliding sport can be done on this 400 meters high hill. This route, which has a 12 km flight band, has the feature of returning to the place of departure and landing due to the slope of the hill and the wind direction. Yelkentepe, which is the only place

where paragliding can be done in the Black Sea region, has a priority place in the preferences of sports lovers.⁸

4.2.5. Linen routes

Linseed cultivation, linen production and linen weaving are carried out in Ayancık district of Sinop Province. In order to revive this tradition, which was on the verge of extinction in the 1990s, the “Traditional Ayancık Festival” was organized and it continues to be held every year in July. “Ayancık Linen Cloth” was included in the list of geographical indications by the Turkish Standards Institute in 2017.⁹ In order to ensure the sustainability of linen yarn production and weaving tradition and to contribute to tourism, the “Journey of Linen in Ayancık” project was developed in cooperation with the Republic of Turkey the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) and Anadolu Efes and in this context, the “Linen Route” was created.¹⁰

With this route, visitors will be transported to the villages where linen farming is carried out, and it will be possible for the visitors to witness the transformation of linen from seed to rope and from rope to weaving, and to bring products to the public with the “Culture, Linen and Wood Festival” where traditional product markets are established. In this context, visitors can participate in the planting and harvesting of linen seeds, and they will also have the chance to experience the process of making and weaving linen thread. While staying in the village, they will be join production and tasting processes of local delicacies, and they will have the opportunity to observe rural life, participate in recreational activities such as nature walks and photosafaris (Öz & Ayhan, 2021: 8-13).

4.2.6. Hourse-riding routes

The province of Sinop has rich areas for horse riding such as around the pond, village roads and forest areas (Kaya, 2015). The tracks prepared by the Sinop Culture and Tourism Directorate for the province with high potential are listed below (Sinop Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism, 2017).

- Sinop Karakum Nisi Pond Area;
- Suluklu Lake Area;
- Boyabat Kalebağı – Salar Villages.

4.2.7. Orienteering routes

Orienteering is a sport based on finding the signs placed in a region with the help of maps and compass, and it is performed in forest areas and natural environments (İmamoğlu et al., 2018). Sinop Province, Hamsilos Nature Park and Akliman Recreation and Picnic Area were added to the map by the Turkish Orienteering Federation by creating a track for orienteering activities. Promising a

⁸ <http://www.gerze.gov.tr/>

⁹ <https://ci.turkpatent.gov.tr/>

¹⁰ <https://www.anadoluefes.com.tr/>

high potential for rural tourism recreation activities, this sport can also be done with bicycles, canoes and motor vehicles (Turkish Orienteering Federation, 2022). The potential track areas for this sport determined by the Sinop Culture and Tourism Directorate are listed below (Sinop Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism, 2017).

- Sinop – Abalı Village – Sogutlu Area;
- Sinop – Bektaşaga Village – Bektaşaga Lake Area;
- Boyabat – Kalebağı Recreation Area.

5. Conclusion

Rural tourism is a type of tourism that plays an important role in protecting the natural environment and transferring it to future generations in terms of its sustainability for the protection of rural areas. Those who want to get rid of the stability of the sea, sand and sun trio in mass tourism have turned to alternative tourism types. Nature-based tourism types have started to be preferred in order to get away from the tiredness of urban life and work stress. It can be said that the attractive feature of rural tourism and its sub-branches creates awareness and gains popularity in the preferences of tourists who want to be intertwined with nature and local activities, and who are also sensitive and conscious of nature (Sillignakis, 2014; İpar & Tırlı, 2014). Especially with the changes in people's travel understanding after the COVID-19 pandemic, the interest in rural tourism branches has increased (Higgins-Desbiolles, 2020). Rural tourism, which has a great contribution to the sustainability of rural areas, provides significant support to the socio-economic development of the local people with accommodation and recreation activities, and to the development of the destination image and reaching more masses.

Sinop Province has a great rural tourism potential as a result of its geographical, historical, cultural, natural and climatic features. The low population rate in the province supports the preservation of sustainability thanks to the presence of natural areas away from the effects of intense industrialization. With all its attractiveness, the number of tourists increasing day by day will gain even more value with promotional and investment activities. The diversity of rural tourism recreational activities will increase with the completion of the projects of the applicable areas and will enable them to reach more audiences. In line with the research, it has been observed that Sinop Province is quite suitable for rural activities, but it has deficiencies such as promotion, infrastructure, investment and planning in evaluating its potential.

Potential rural tourism recreational activities areas of the city: to focus on the promotion of cultural values, to increase and develop the activities that will present the existing cultural values, activating new natural area facilities to be opened for tourism, increasing education and incentives for the local people who mostly live on agriculture and livestock, to combine their own businesses with rural tourism to contribute to both tourism and their own economy, ensuring the initiative, investment and infrastructure of events such as more national and international

competitions and festivals for recreational activities are among the recommendations of the study.

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